

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Farm Diversification and its Role in achieving Safe and Just Outcomes: Insights from German FADN Data *Discussion paper*

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Farm Diversification and its Role in achieving Safe and Just Outcomes: Insights from German FADN Data

-Discussion paper-

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Introduction/ Problem Statement

Intensive agricultural systems significantly drive environmental degradation, including land-cover change, greenhouse gas emissions and biodiversity loss (Foley et al., 2005; Beddington et al., 2012; Campbell et al., 2017; Jones et al., 2023, Gerten and Kummu, 2021). Provisional estimates by Campbell et al. (2017) suggest that the way the world currently produces food contributes to >80% of transgressions of terrestrial planetary boundaries and ~25% of transgressions of the climate change boundary (Gerten and Kummu, 2021).

Farm diversity is increasingly recognized as a promising pathway to a more ecologically sustainable food production (Rasmussen et al., 2024). Studies on net zero pathways show that strategies to diversify farming systems by managing multiple species, incorporating areas of non-crop vegetation, or conserving soil or water have been posed as ways of countering the negative environmental effects of simplified agriculture such as biodiversity loss and pollution (FABLE, 2022; Rasmussen et al., 2024; Jones et al., 2021). Many options and opportunities exist to produce and consume food in a more sustainable “safe” way (Gerten and Kummu, 2021). These include yield-gap closure, i.e., improved water, soil, and nutrient-management practices that can be applied (ideally in combination) by farmers (Gerten and Kummu, 2021)¹. However, such discussions often overlook “just” outcomes, leading to policies that fail to address socio-economic dimensions sufficiently. The “just” transformations describe major aspects of social, economic and cultural life necessary to mitigate the climate and biodiversity emergencies in particular. These transitions require strong structural, technical and behavioural change

¹ These methods mainly comprise water conservation and water-use efficiency increase through rainwater harvesting, upgraded irrigation systems and soil-conservation techniques, restoration of degraded soils, and increased nitrogen-use efficiency. The yield-gap closure together with reductions in food waste “from field to fork” and adoption of diets with less animal-based products and proteins by individual consumers could double the food supply without using more land and water. In Africa and South Asia yield-gap closure is the most optimal solution, whereas in most parts of Europe and North America dietary change has the largest potential (Gerten and Kummu, 2021).

in production, distribution and consumption in many sectors of the economy and society (Baldock and Buckwell, 2021).

Consequently, reconciling productivity with safe and just (SJ) outcomes is essential for current and future generations (Rasmussen et al., 2024; Jones et al., 2023; Rosa-Schleich, 2019). In this study, we therefore aim to investigate whether a specific degree and type of farm diversification aligns with SJ outcomes such as environmental sustainability, resource efficiency and farm resilience. Incorporating diversification could allow farmers to reduce environmental impact, enhance their economic resilience, and contribute to more equitable agricultural systems. To address this, we propose a novel concept to measure farm diversification based on the distribution of three farm resources: land, labor and capital. Using Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) data, we construct diversification indices that quantify the evenness of resource use across farm activities, enabling an overall diversification measure per farm. Compared to existing approaches, our concept offers a more holistic perspective on farm diversification and its contribution to achieving SJ outcomes.

Approach

When considering SJ outcomes, not only are environmental benefits relevant, but also economic and social ones. Hence, to determine whether there are advantages to scaling up diversified agricultural systems, evidence is needed that diversification does not privilege certain outcomes (e.g., nonagricultural biodiversity) at the expense of others (e.g., yields) (Rasmussen et al., 2024). Using a five-step methodology, we (1) identify diversification strategies from existing literature, (2) map FADN variables to resource-use shifts, (3) construct diversification indices using the Shannon-Weaver Index, (4) examine temporal trends, and (5) map these trends to SJ outcome indicators.

Step 1: Identify relevant diversification strategies

To identify relevant diversification strategies, we reviewed the major meta-analyses undertaken by Rasmussen et al. (2024) and Tamburini et al. (2020) that examine the effects of diversification practices on environmental and social outcomes, both separately and in combination. The regarded ecosystem services are biodiversity, water regulation, carbon sequestration, climate regulation, nutrient cycling, soil fertility, pollination, pest control, human well-being, food security and crop yield. The assessment focused on five types of diversification strategies: (i) crop diversification (e.g. crop rotation and cover crops), (ii) non-crop diversification (e.g. habitats within or around the field), (iii) soil management and fertility management (e.g. adding organic material and reduced tillage), (iv) livestock inclusion and diversification, and (v) organic farming (production systems free of synthetic pesticides and mineral fertilizers). Both analyses used the currently dominant industrial farming system as control practice.

The results of both meta-analyses show that the impact of agricultural diversification on biodiversity and ecosystem services was predominantly positive. Enhancing the diversity of biological communities through applying diversification strategies can increase resource use efficiency and the stability of ecosystem production over time (Tamburini et al., 2020). Soil health improves through crop rotation, intercropping, and polycultures, which help reduce erosion, maintain nutrients, and enhance biodiversity. Diverse farming systems can improve water efficiency, promote natural pest control, and reduce the need for synthetic inputs, all of which contribute to operating within the ecological "safe" limits (Tamburini et al., 2020).

Diversification can also contribute to the "just" part of the operating space by promoting equitable practices and addressing social issues within agriculture:

- Smallholder empowerment: Diversified farming systems often require less capital investment than industrial-scale monocultures, making it more accessible to small-scale farmers.
- Working conditions: Farms that are more diversified often require a wider range of skills and offer more stable, year-round employment opportunities.

Diversification allows farmers to become more economically stable, which is crucial in navigating the uncertainties of modern farming (Vroege et al., 2020). By not relying on a single crop or product, farmers spread the risk associated with market fluctuations, climate change, or disease outbreaks (Vroege et al., 2020). Additionally, diversified farms are often better positioned to enter niche or specialty markets, such as organic produce or value-added products, which can boost profitability while meeting consumer demand for sustainable options. Farm diversification is therefore an important aspect of agricultural and rural development policy in Europe as it allows farm households to exploit their resources more broadly (Vroege et al., 2020).

Overall, applying a high number of diversification strategies or practices is associated with more potential for a positive impact on biodiversity, yield, environmental and social outcome variables (Rasmussen et al., 2024). Diversified farming (DF) systems should therefore integrate ecological and economic benefits which supports farm survival, creates new economic opportunities and services in rural regions and contributes to the resilience and sustainability of farming systems (Vroege et al., 2020; Rosa-Schleich, 2019; Tamburini et al., 2020). Farm diversification thereby implies a shift of farm resources (land, labour or capital) away from an intensification on single crops or livestock towards diversifying primary agricultural activities and/or non-agricultural farm-based activities (Vroege et al., 2020; Van der Ploeg and Roep, 2003).

On-farm activities (OFA) thereby concern agricultural farming practices and landscapes that intentionally include functional biodiversity at multiple spatial and/or temporal scales in order to

maintain ecosystem services that provide critical inputs to agriculture, such as soil fertility, pest and disease control, water use efficiency, and pollination (Kremen et al., 2012; Jones et al., 2023). Non-agricultural farm-based other gainful activities (OGA) activities are however related to the rural area dimension of the farm enterprise. These activities create new sources of income that are not related primarily to agriculture (Van der Ploeg and Roep, 2003).

Building on the existing literature, our concept measures the degree of farm diversification based on the use of the resource land, labor, and capital within the farm activities. Farms with a more even distribution of resource usage are considered to be more diversified.

Step 2: Identify the underlying processes regarding resource usage & map with FADN variables

To operationalize the concept in step (1), we derive the underlying processes of the main diversification practices with regards to the necessary resource usage amongst farms through reviewing indicators previously used in literature on indicator-based sustainability assessment of livestock and crop farming as well as non-agricultural farm-based other gainful activities. Previous reviews have covered these three farm activity areas (Vroege et al., 2020; Van der Ploeg and Roep, 2003) and the use of the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database for indicator construction (Robling et al., 2023).

Farm diversification can be depicted through capital-related processes such as an increase of income sources showing investments in new OFAs or OGAs. Additionally, external subsidies such as agri-environment, organic farming or rural development payments are often required to support diversification.

Land-related process can be seen in the reallocation of land for new uses, the implementation of sustainable practices, or the change in land tenure. Further, taking changes in woodland area (not included in utilized agricultural area) into account indicates a potential shift from OFAs to OGAs.

Increasing farm diversity involves also a diversification of the farmers and workers labour force. New skill development as well as adjusting workforce allocation is required as workforce demand shifts. Further additional workforce may be needed depending on the original workload. These shifts can be seen in labour pattern of paid and unpaid labour as well as workforce allocated to OGA work.

Each of these processes interacts dynamically, requiring careful planning to ensure that farm diversification leads to sustainable and profitable outcomes. Mapping FADN variables with the occurring resource usage pattern allows to quantify the land, labor and capital allocation to occurring farm activities. We receive the following matrix:

Table 1: FADN variables for resource use measures

Resource use	FADN Farm activity variables			
	crop	livestock	OGA	
Capital ('000 €/farm)	Cereals (Common wheat, Durum wheat, Rye, Barley, Oat, Maize)	Cows' milk & milk products	Forestry and wood processing	
	Protein crops (peas, lentils)	Beef and veal	Contractual work	
	Potatoes	Pigmeat	Agritourism	
	Sugar beet	Sheep & goats' meat	Renewable Energy	
	Oil-seed crops	Poultrymeat		
	Industrial crops	Eggs		
	Vegetables & flowers	Ewes' & goats' milk		
	Fruit	Other livestock		
	Wine & grapes	Forage crops		
	Other crops			
	Agri-environment payments			
	Organic farming subsidy payment			
	Rural development payments			
Labour (AWU/farm)	Manager paid/unpaid		Holder Unpaid/Paid	
	Other paid/unpaid			
	Holder unpaid			
	Spouse unpaid			
Land (ha/farm)	Common wheat	Permanent grassland	Woodland not in UAA	
	Durum wheat	Temporary grassland	Other land	
	Rye	Green maize		
	Barley	Other green crops		
	Oats	Other root crops		
	Grain maize	Leguminous		
	Field peas	Tritical		
	Lentils	Fallow land without sub		
	Potatoes	Fallow land with sub		
	Sugar beet			
	Rape			
	Sunflower			
	Soya			
	Linseed			
	Other oil seed			
	Hops			
	Medicinal crops			
	Vegetables and fruit			
	Vineyards			
	Orchards			
	Other permanent crops			
	Seeds & seedlings			

Based on the scientific literature review and the underlying processes, we mapped 33, 7 and 31 FADN variables to land, labor, and capital use, respectively. For land, the variables capture the different land-use categories (e.g., arable, woodland, and other land) as well as specific land-use practices (e.g. cereals, grassland and permanent crops). For labor, the variables distinguish between different labor types, such as paid/unpaid and holder/spouse labor. For capital, the variables indicate the main income sources ranging from primary agricultural activities (e.g., crop and livestock production) to non-agricultural farm-based activities (e.g., agritourism and contractual work). This mapping enables a comprehensive assessment of resource use at the farm level.

Step 3: Set up diversification index for each resource

Since our analysis considered the farm as the level of analysis, we use farm-level data, specifically FADN data. The FADN network comprises nearly 80,000 farms that represent a population of about 5 million farms (European Commission, 2023). Our study utilizes German FADN data from 8,400 farms annually between 2014 and 2021. Overall, at the national level, there are 32,200 observations in our dataset. FADN monitors farm-level economic indicators and provides a comprehensive source of harmonized microeconomic data for EU's commercial farms, derived from national surveys (European Commission, 2024; Thuenen Institute, 2012). Its methodology ensures representativeness across three key dimensions: region, economic size and type of farming (European Commission, 2024; Thuenen Institute, 2012). Such a system enables the comparison of respective farm data at national, regional, and European levels (FAO, 2024).

To measure the degree of diversification per farm and year, we apply the Shannon-Weaver Index for each of the three resource categories: land, labor and capital. Contrary to former studies which used the Simpson or Gini index, our index will not only account for the richness (number of activities) but also the evenness (distribution of available resources among the activities) of a farm diversification (Strong, 2016). Using the Shannon index allows for more rare activities to affect the index in a similar way than dominant farm activities. This allows for an understanding of changes in resource patterns that have not been determined yet.

Denoted as $H_{f,t,r}$, this index is calculated as:

$$H_{f,t,r} = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_{i,f,t,r} * \ln(p_{i,f,t,r})$$

Where $p_{i,f,t,r}$ is the proportion of the resource used in the i -th activity with regards to the total land, labor or capital (r) available for each farm (f) and year (t) (Spellerberg and Fedor, 2003). Total evenness of resource use amongst farm activities is measured as the natural logarithm of the total number of farm activities.

Step 4: Analyse diversification indices over time

To identify diversification patterns and assess variability of trends over time, descriptive analyses such as diversity classifications, distribution trends and group comparisons are carried out on:

- evenness of diversification indices over time (2014 – 2021)
- Transition matrix between 2014 and 2021: farm categorization by type over time
- Diversification characteristics of farms that change farm type to those that do not

Step 5: Comparison of diversity patterns with SJ outcomes

Recently, several studies have shown first attempts to map available indicators with the thematic areas of the safe and just operating space concept. Mueller et al. (2024) have mapped existing and very specific model indicators with the SJOS indicator domains to include SJOS domains generally in modelling exercises. Others, such as Roblin et al. (2023) and Arndt and Helming (2025), have mapped sustainability indicators with FADN indicators to measure sustainability at a farm level.

Thematic area	SJOS Indicator Domain	FADN indicator	Reference
Biodiversity	Functional diversity (on-farm)	Rough grazing to farmed area	Arndt & Helming (2025) Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023)
		Organic area	Arndt & Helming (2025)
Land use	Land cover	Agricultural area (UAA)	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Coppola et al. (2022) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
	Land use	Land diversification index	Arndt & Helming (2025) Coppola et al. (2022) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
	Land use intensity/ Land management	SE120 Stocking density	Arndt & Helming (2025) Robling et al. (2023) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
	Land system change/ Rich agricultural landscape	SE074 Voluntary and compulsory set aside	Arndt & Helming (2025) Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023)
Biogeochemical flows: Nutrient flows	Nitrogen cycle	SE296 N Fertilizer	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
	Phosphorus cycle	SE297 P Fertilizer	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
	Kalium cycle	SE298 K Fertilizer	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
Chemical pollution	Pesticide use	IPROT_V Crop production products	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
Climate impact	Carbon sequestration & storage	SE028 Permanent grassland to temporary grass area - ratio	Robling et al. (2023)
Health	Animal welfare	SE310 Feed purchase to permanent pasture	Robling et al. (2023)
		IVET_V Veterinary expenses	Robling et al. (2023)
Social equity	Human capital & education	SE623 Support to help farmers adapt/ training	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
	Recreational landscapes/ Regional development	SE624 Total support for rural development	Arndt & Helming (2025) Mueller et al. (2024)
	Eco-system services/ Regional development	SAEAWSUB_2_V Environmental subsidies (€)	Arndt & Helming (2025) Robling et al. (2023) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
Farm resilience	Farm income	SE430 Family farm Income (€)	Mueller et al. (2024) Coppola et al. (2022)
	Farm structure	Ratio owned UAA to rented UAA	Own
		SE022 Share of OGA work in AWU	Arndt & Helming (2025)
	Work-life balance	SE010 Total labour input	Robling et al. (2023)
		Ratio holder&Spouse to other&manager	Own
Farm household vulnerability	Ratio on-farm to off-farm income	Arndt & Helming (2025) Robling et al. (2023) Coppola et al. (2022)	

		Capital diversification index	Arndt & Helming (2025) Coppola et al. (2022) Dabkiene et al. (2021)
Economy	Sectoral wages	SE370 Wages paid to labour	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Coppola et al (2022)
	Sectoral Employment/ rural employment opportunities	SE020 Paid labour input (AWU/farm) Of manager and other	Mueller et al. (2024) Robling et al. (2023) Coppola et al. (2022)
		SYS02 Number of farms	Robling et al. (2023)
	Sectoral vulnerability	Labour diversification index	Arndt & Helming (2025) Coppola et al. (2022)

Mapping diversification data with SJ indicators such as nitrogen use and rural employment opportunities provides a comprehensive understanding of how farm diversification aligns with improved socio-economic outcomes such as job creation, resource sustainability, and resilience over time.

Results

Farm Diversification Trends

The diversification trends of capital, labour, and land resources from 2014 to 2021 reveal that diversification remains stable over time. Dividing the farms depending on their respective diversification index into top 10%, middle 10% and bottom 10% allows for a more differentiated insight into diversification patterns.

When compared with the natural log of the evenness values, the indices for middle diversification farms reach about one-third of these maximum values, reflecting limited distribution of resources across different activities.

Natural log of the evenness of a resource usage (H_{max})

$$H_{max,capital} = 3.43$$

$$H_{max,labour} = 1.95$$

$$H_{max,land} = 3.49$$

While these middle-level farms show only slight increases over time, high diversification farms, particularly in the case of labour, achieve relatively higher evenness values. This hints that although most farms remain concentrated in their resource allocation, certain highly diversified farms are better able to balance their use of labour, contributing greater flexibility and resilience.

Looking at each resource individually generates an even clearer pattern of relevant diversification strategies.

Capital

The graph illustrates the diversification trends of capital use from 2014 to 2021, grouped again according to the diversification level of the farms into top 10%, middle 10% and bottom 10%. The graph effectively combines violin plots and mean trend lines, allowing both distribution spread and central

tendencies to be observed simultaneously. The violin plots show the distribution of diversification values within each group over time, while the lines with markers represent the mean values for each group.

Figure 1: Capital Diversification over time (2014 - 2021)

The top farms consistently record the highest diversification levels, with values fluctuating around 1.7 – 1.9, while the middle 10% maintain moderate levels around 1.0 in 2014 up to 1.2 in 2021. In contrast, the bottom farms remain close to zero throughout the period, reflecting very limited diversification.

The violin shapes indicate variability within each group, with the top 10% showing the widest distributions across years, suggesting a more heterogeneous trend among highly diversified farms over time. The middle 10% display narrower distributions with slight increases toward 2021. The bottom 10% farms, however, remain stable and tightly clustered around minimal diversification values.

This clearly highlights the persistence of differences across farms with regard to capital distribution, while also showing that the overall trends remain stable over time with only a small increase.

The transition matrix illustrates how farms shift between different farm types depending on whether capital diversification increased or decreased between 2014 and 2021. The diagonal values are notably high, showing that most farms tend to remain in the same farm type over time rather than undergoing major transitions, even if they increase their income diversification. In several cases, the persistence rates exceed 90%, which highlights a strong tendency for farms to maintain their existing structure of capital use. This suggests that changes in diversification occur mainly through an increase in OGA instead of OGF.

Figure 2: Farm Type Capital Transition matrix between 2014 and 2021

C A P I T A L	Farming Types 2014	Farming Types 2021													
		Total number	Capital diversification	Crop	Other Crops	Horticulture	Wine	Orchards	Permanent crops	Milk	Sheep/Goats	Cattle	Granivores	Mixed crops	Mixed livestock
	Crop	488	↑(45%) ↓(55%)	78%	14%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3%	0%	4%
	Other Crops	283	↑(45%) ↓(55%)	5%	89%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	2%	0%	3%
	Horticulture	73	↑(62%) ↓(38%)	2%	0%	91%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	2%
	Wine	232	↑(37%) ↓(63%)	0%	0%	0%	99%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%	0%
	Orchards	39	↑(41%) ↓(59%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	88%	0%	0%	0%	0%	13%	0%	0%
	Permanent crops	13	↑(46%) ↓(54%)	17%	33%	0%	17%	0%	33%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Milk	1205	↑(50%) ↓(50%)	1%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	80%	0%	7%	0%	0%	8%
	Sheep/Goats	39	↑(46%) ↓(54%)	6%	50%	0%	0%	0%	0%	22%	22%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	Cattle	364	↑(48%) ↓(52%)	2%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	5%	1%	81%	1%	7%	4%
	Granivores	423	↑(78%) ↓(22%)	7%	5%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	70%	0%	17%
	Mixed crops	56	↑(32%) ↓(68%)	0%	6%	0%	22%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	72%	0%
	Mixed livestock	189	↑(49%) ↓(51%)	1%	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2%	0%	11%	0%	65%	17%
	Crops/Livestock	516	↑(44%) ↓(56%)	13%	20%	0%	0%	0%	0%	4%	0%	1%	4%	3%	55%

However, transitions away from the diagonal do exist, with probabilities in the range of 20-30%, but these are much smaller compared to the overwhelming likelihood of staying in the same category. If we see changes, it is away from livestock towards a more diverse crop production system.

Labour

When compared with total evenness of labour use ($H_{max,labour} = 1.95$), the graph indicates that the top 10% farms are strongly and evenly diversified, although we see a downward trend from 2014 to 2021. This indicates that in the last years we have experienced a concentration with regards to labour allocation towards farm family members.

The middle 10% remain stable at around 0.7, while the bottom 10% stay near zero throughout time, showing minimal diversification in labour use.

Figure 3: Labour Diversification over time (2014 - 2021)

The presentation of these trends makes the gap between actual and potential diversification very clear. This suggests a strong reliance on predominantly farmers' and family labour rather than paid labour.

In the labour transition matrix, there is a strong persistence of farms within the same farm types between 2014 and 2021, as shown by the high percentages along the diagonal. Farms specialized in labour-intensive activities such as horticulture or dairy remain almost entirely in their farm type. This reflects the structural rigidity of how farms allocate and organize their workforce and that specialised labour cannot be moved easily into a new production system.

Figure 4: Farm Type Labour Transition matrix between 2014 and 2021

Farming Types 2014	Farming Types 2021														
	Total farm number	Labour diversification	Crop	Other Crops	Horticulture	Wine	Orchards	Permanent crops	Milk	Sheep/ Goats	Cattle	Granivores	Mixed crops	Mixed livestock	Crops/ Livestock
Crop	480	↑(53%) ↓(47%)	75%	19%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2%	0%	4%
Other Crops	287	↑(52%) ↓(48%)	5%	90%	1%	0%	0%	1%	0%	0%	1%	1%	1%	0%	1%
Horticulture	71	↑(49%) ↓(51%)	3%	0%	94%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3%	0%	0%
Wine	227	↑(47%) ↓(53%)	0%	0%	0%	98%	0%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%	0%
Orchards	39	↑(49%) ↓(51%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	79%	11%	0%	0%	0%	0%	11%	0%	0%
Permanent crops	13	↑(46%) ↓(54%)	17%	0%	0%	33%	0%	50%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Milk	1176	↑(46%) ↓(54%)	1%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	84%	1%	6%	0%	0%	0%	5%
Sheep/Goats	37	↑(49%) ↓(51%)	0%	56%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	33%	11%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Cattle	352	↑(47%) ↓(53%)	2%	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	10%	1%	77%	1%	0%	2%	5%
Granivores	419	↑(48%) ↓(52%)	6%	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	69%	0%	1%	19%
Mixed crops	59	↑(54%) ↓(46%)	0%	9%	3%	28%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	56%	0%	0%
Mixed livestock	187	↑(45%) ↓(55%)	1%	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	14%	0%	7%	10%	0%	46%	18%
Crops/Livestock	535	↑(50%) ↓(50%)	11%	21%	0%	0%	0%	0%	5%	0%	2%	6%	2%	2%	51%

Even mixed or crop-based farms show relatively strong persistence, though with slightly lower percentages compared to the specialized farm types. Farms appear locked in their original farm type, reflecting a strong path dependency.

Land

The land diversification graph illustrates that the top10% consistently have the highest values, averaging close to 2.0. Only minor fluctuations across the years are seen, indicating a relatively stable pattern of land diversification. Between the 3 resource usages, these values are the highest. The middle 10% farms maintain values around 1.2 – 1.3, showing small increases in early years but generally stable afterwards. The bottom 10% see a strong increase between 2015 and 2016, but still remain close to zero. This suggests that these farms allocate their land resources in a highly concentrated manner with little diversification across activities.

Figure 5: Land Diversification over time (2014 - 2021)

Although among the three resources, land exhibits the most significant increase in diversification, when compared to the maximum possible diversification value for land ($H_{max,land} = 3.49$), the results highlight the significant gap between actual diversification levels and theoretical evenness. This underlines the fact that while some diversification is evident, particularly among the top 10%, farms are still far from a highly diversified land use.

The diagonal values of the land transition matrix are notably high, with most farm types maintaining strong stability in their land use strategy. This highlights the relatively entrenched nature of land allocation, where structural changes in how land is used across farm activities are limited.

Figure 6: Farm Type Land Transition matrix between 2014 and 2021

Farming Types 2014	Total number	Land diversification	Farming Types 2021												
			Crop	Other Crops	Horticulture	Wine	Orchards	Permanent crops	Milk	Sheep/Goats	Cattle	Granivores	Mixed crops	Mixed livestock	Crops/Livestock
Crop	506	↑(57%) ↓(43%)	79%	16%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2%	0%	3%
Other Crops	293	↑(48%) ↓(52%)	4%	88%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2%	2%	0%	4%
Horticulture	65	↑(82%) ↓(18%)	2%	0%	96%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2%	0%	0%
Wine	180	↑(71%) ↓(29%)	0%	0%	0%	98%	0%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	0%	0%
Orchards	39	↑(72%) ↓(28%)	0%	0%	0%	0%	79%	0%	7%	0%	0%	0%	14%	0%	0%
Permanent crops	13	↑(62%) ↓(38%)	13%	0%	0%	50%	0%	38%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Milk	1215	↑(41%) ↓(59%)	1%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	84%	0%	6%	0%	0%	0%	5%
Sheep/Goats	36	↑(46%) ↓(54%)	4%	32%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	48%	12%	0%	0%	0%	4%
Cattle	366	↑(47%) ↓(53%)	2%	5%	0%	0%	0%	0%	8%	2%	73%	1%	0%	3%	8%
Granivores	434	↑(65%) ↓(35%)	5%	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	72%	0%	1%	19%
Mixed crops	60	↑(30%) ↓(70%)	0%	17%	0%	17%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	67%	0%	0%
Mixed livestock	191	↑(46%) ↓(54%)	3%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	5%	0%	7%	13%	0%	53%	16%
Crops/Livestock	553	↑(47%) ↓(53%)	17%	18%	0%	0%	0%	0%	3%	0%	2%	7%	3%	1%	50%

What stands out most is the patterns of upward and downward movements. On the one hand, some farm types show a strong likelihood of increasing land diversification such as horticulture, wine or orchards, with probabilities as high as 82% in certain cases. On the other hand. Some farm types show significant downward movements such as mixed crop farms, where 70% decrease their diversification over time. This contrast between stability on the diagonal and notable shifts in diversification trends for particular farm types suggest that major changes are likely driven by external pressures such as market opportunities, land availability, or policy incentives.

Summary

Although farm diversification is seen as an important strategy to a more sustainable food production, the identified diversification trend of the three regarded farm resources is considerably smaller than expected.

Capital diversification remains stable over time, with middle 10% farms reaching only about one-third of the maximum possible evenness, while the top 10% farms achieve higher but still limited values. Labour diversification shows relatively high values, especially among the top 10% farms. Land diversification remains steady over the years.

The transition matrices all show a strong remain of the farms along the diagonal, meaning most farms stay within the same farm type over time. Labour allocation anchors farms in their original types, while capital shows greater mobility, allowing for more transitions between farm types. Labour is far less flexible and does not easily adapt to structural changes or diversification strategies.

The observed upward trend in diversification, therefore, mainly occurs through an increase and diversification in OGA. At the same time, changes in farm type can be observed where farms move away from livestock production systems towards more diverse crop production systems.

Safe and Just Outcomes

The circular bar chart represents the performance of farms in 2014 in relation to the “Safe” and “Just” boundaries of sustainability indicators. Each circular bar chart depicts one of three farm diversification degrees: top 10%, middle 10%, bottom 10%. The diversification degree is calculated through a total diversification index over all determined resource indicators under step 2. Diversification is thereby not divided by the use of resources anymore. The bars radiating outward show the 2014 data values for each indicator, such as farm income, labour, fertilizer use, land ratios, and support payments. The black circle for the just and safe indicators marks the average values in 2014 across all farms, serving as a baseline for comparison. Indicators are grouped conceptually around the two dimensions: “Just” on the left and “Safe” on the right.

The arrows indicate the direction of change from 2014 to 2021. Green arrows represent improvement or movement towards greater sustainability, while red arrows represent a worsening from the perspective of the safe and just boundaries.

Top 10%

For the top 10% farms, we can see that in 2014, just indicators were above the average, suggesting a stable socioeconomic surrounding, but at the same time, safe indicators were generally used beyond average.

In 2021, ecological improvements can be seen in fertilizer usage, area of set aside land, sequestration, and stocking density. Socioeconomic improvements are seen in farm income, % OGA work, wages, and number of farms. An increase in support payments not only help stabilized the just dimension but also shows an ecological improvement over time.

From the graph, we can derive that while highly diversified farms generally maintain strong performance on “Just” indicators, their “Safe” indicators related to resource use and environmental impact generally improve between 2014 and 2021. This suggests that a strong diversification allows farms to systematically change their resource management, achieving a balance between social equity and ecological safety in agriculture. This potentially reflects the use of more resource-efficient practices.

Middle 10%

From the graph, we see that the development regarding the safe and just indicators is far less positive than for the top 10% farms. Especially, ecological indicators such as fertilizer use and land management experience a negative shift over time. The total number of farms in this group also declines. On the other hand “Just” indicators like farm income, support, and farm adaptability (% OGA work, wages) improve. Overall, this suggests that moderately diversified farms achieve an improvement in social sustainability at the expense of environmental sustainability.

Bottom 10%

Compared to the other two diversification groups, the bars for the bottom 10% farms are generally lower meaning below total average. This indicates lower starting values in many variables. Regarding the trend up to 2021, especially for “Safe” indicators, the bottom 10% farms demonstrate a negative shift. Environmental indicators such as fertilizer use, pesticides, land management, organic area show a worsening potentially due to higher usage or less efficient management. On the “Just” side, however, we see an improvement in farm income, wages, and annual working hours. The economic growth, therefore, seems to come at the expense of environmental indicators.

Discussion and conclusion

Analyzing the diversification trends of German farms highlights the potential benefits and limitations of diversification strategies in the agricultural sector. The results show a strong tendency for farms to keep their agricultural production structures, showing diversification tendency mainly towards OGAs. The transition matrices confirm this locked-in trend with high diagonal values which indicate that diversification trend occur within the farm specialization. While the top 10% of farms consistently demonstrate higher levels of diversification, particularly in their resource use of capital and land, the middle 10% only show a moderate diversification trend, and the bottom 10% undertake very little diversification strategies. This implies that farm structures are the main driver of how farms allocate their resources, resulting in diversification being concentrated among a rather small number of farms.

Labour appears to be the most adamant factor, with limited ability to adapt to new production systems due to specialization effects. Even highly diversified farms in terms of labour experience a decline in the diversification index over time. This indicates a growing reliance on family labour rather than paid labour. In contrast, the resource use of capital and land seems to be more flexible, though the levels of diversification remain well below their potential maximum value. Notably, land diversification has the highest diversification index values among the three resources, but even here, the gap between actual and potential evenness is significant. This adds on to the finding that diversification strategies in farming remain limited, with external factors like market forces, land availability, and policy incentives necessary to drive meaningful change.

Consolidating the safe and just framework with the diversification trend of farms allows to highlight the effects of diversification on the sustainability of farms. The top 10% of farms regarding diversification experience improvements in "Just" indicators like farm income and wages as well as ecological gains in resource efficiency, fertilizer reduction, and set-aside land. This indicates that a higher diversification rate may allow farms to better balance social and ecological goals. In the long-run, this builds resilience while reducing environmental pressures. The middle 10% show mixed results, improving in social sustainability but facing setbacks in ecological indicators, which highlights trade-offs when diversification does not occur in all areas of farm resource usage. The bottom 10% improve economically over time but at the cost of a reduced environmental performance, highlighting the effects of low diversification trend on the long-term sustainability of farms.

Our paper shows that diversification remains a limited but valuable strategy in agricultural development. A balanced diversification strategy holds promise not just for farm resilience but also for advancing safe and just sustainability outcomes in agriculture. While the overall trends are stable, the performance of highly diversified farms suggests that better resource allocation enhances adaptability, resilience, and sustainability outcomes. However, most farms remain locked in their current farm specialization, with labour being the least flexible resource.

In order to enhance broader as well as deeper diversification, diversification policies and incentives could help close the gap between current and potential diversification levels. Further, research should take a closer look at the underlying factors that explain why some farms achieve higher levels of diversification while others remain stuck in low-diversification patterns. Comparative analysis across regions and farm types would help to understand the role of structural factors in shaping resource allocation. Moreover, studies that combine socioeconomic data with environmental performance indicators would be helpful for identifying the optimal level of diversification that improves both "safe" and "just" outcomes.

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Conflicts of interest/ Competing interests

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this article

Ethics approval/ Consent to participate/Consent for publication

Not applicable to this article as no human participants involved during the current study.

Availability of data

The data cannot be published due to confidentiality requirements.

Authors' contributions

Conceptualization, L.A. and H.S.; Methodology, L.A. and H.S.; Resources, L.A, T.K. and H.S; Writing – original draft preparation, L.A. and H.S.; Writing – review and editing, L.A, T.K. and H.S; Visualization, L.A.; Project administration, L.A. and H.S.; Funding acquisition, H.S.

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